

ENERGY AND ENTROPY ANALYSIS FOR MATERIAL DEFORMATION PROCESSES**Ekin Can KAYAR**

Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Institute of Science, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ankara-Türkiye

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-4191-587X>

Ali ABDEL JAWAD

Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ankara-Türkiye

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4271-5643>

Ünal ÇAMDALI

Prof. Dr., Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ankara-Türkiye

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2566-9945>

Abstract

Understanding how materials interact with external effects such as force, temperature and time is essential for achieving efficient, reliable and energy-aware engineering design. The response of materials to deformation involves fundamental energy processes, including mechanical energy storage, dissipation and irreversible energy conversion. Accurate modeling of elastic, viscous, plastic and anelastic deformation mechanisms enables the prediction of energy loss, deformation limits and overall structural performance. In this study, the thermomechanical and energy-related behavior of materials is examined using rheological systems composed of idealized mechanical elements: the elastic spring, viscous dashpot and friction element. These elements represent recoverable energy storage, rate-dependent energy dissipation and irreversible energy loss mechanisms within the material. The deformation response of the system is investigated under steady, unsteady and load-reversal conditions, emphasizing how mechanical energy is partitioned into stored, recoverable and dissipated components.

Elastic deformation allows full recovery of stored mechanical energy, whereas viscous and frictional mechanisms convert a portion of the external work into irreversible energy losses. Only the reversible part of the mechanical energy contributes to the thermodynamic state, while the irreversible part appears as dissipated energy. Using the mechanical energy balance combined with the Clausius–Duhem inequality, expressions for entropy generation are derived in direct relation to these energy-conversion processes. During mechanical hysteresis cycles, non-coinciding loading and unloading curves quantify the irreversible energy loss, which transforms into heat and increases the entropy of the surroundings. The results demonstrate that rheological systems provide a robust framework for analyzing energy conversion mechanisms, irreversible deformation behavior and entropy generation in thermomechanical materials, making the approach relevant for energy-focused engineering applications.

Keywords: Energy Dissipation, Thermomechanical Behavior, Material Deformation, Entropy Generation, Energy Conversion.

Nomenclature

σ	Stress, Pa
σ_{ij}	Components of the Cauchy Stress Tensor, Pa
ε	Strain
ε_{ij}	Strain Tensor
$\dot{\varepsilon}$	Strain Rate, s^{-1}
ε_e	Elastic Strain Component
μ	Viscosity Coefficient (Dashpot), $Pa \cdot s$
U	Elastic Potential Energy, J
t	Time, s
α	Time-Dependent Loading Coefficient, $Pa \cdot s^{-1}$
ρ	Density, $kg \cdot m^{-3}$
v	Velocity, $m \cdot s^{-1}$
f	Body Force per Unit Mass, $N \cdot kg^{-1}$
e	Internal Energy per Unit Mass, $J \cdot kg^{-1}$
q	Heat Flux Vector, $W \cdot m^{-2}$
s	Entropy per Unit Mass, $J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$
s'_{gen}	Entropy Generation Rate, $J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1} \cdot s^{-1}$
T	Temperature, K
V	Control Volume, m^3
A	Control Surface Area, m^2
k	Spring Stiffness Coefficient, $N \cdot m^{-1}$
c	Damping Coefficient, $N \cdot s \cdot m^{-1}$
m	Mass, kg

Introduction

The thermomechanical behavior of solid materials is governed by the interaction between elastic energy storage mechanisms and irreversible processes that lead to energy dissipation. While elastic deformation enables reversible storage of mechanical energy, viscous and plastic behaviors result in energy loss, permanent deformation, and entropy generation. Therefore, a consistent description of deformation processes requires the combined use of continuum mechanics and the fundamental principles of thermodynamics [1].

Continuum thermodynamics provides this framework by linking the balance laws of mass, momentum, and energy with the entropy balance. The second law of thermodynamics, expressed through the Clausius–Duhem inequality, imposes fundamental restrictions on admissible material behavior by requiring that irreversible processes occur with non-negative entropy production. In this context, a direct relationship exists between mechanical energy dissipation and entropy generation [2].

Rheological models offer an effective approach for representing complex material behavior using idealized mechanical elements with clear physical interpretations. Elastic springs represent energy storage, dashpots model viscous dissipation, and friction elements account for permanent deformation. Multi-element rheological models constructed from these components provide an efficient framework for analyzing time-dependent deformation, hysteresis, and energy loss mechanisms [3].

In this study, a three-element rheological model with a topology similar to the 3M12 structure is numerically investigated. The elastic, viscous, and plastic contributions of the model are evaluated within a unified framework, and the resulting displacement, energy, and entropy responses are analyzed in light of the underlying theoretical principles. The study aims to demonstrate the thermodynamic consistency of the model by directly relating energy dissipation to entropy generation [4].

Studies focusing on the investigation of the thermomechanical behavior of materials in the context of energy storage, energy dissipation, and irreversible processes occupy a significant place in the literature. Özdemir, M., examined the energy accumulation and energy dissipation mechanisms that arise during the deformation processes of solid materials within a thermodynamic framework. In the study, the effects of elastic, viscous, and plastic behaviors on energy conversion processes were theoretically addressed; in particular, the relationship between mechanical work, internal energy increase, and irreversible dissipation was evaluated through analytical models. The obtained results contributed significantly to the energy-based explanation of hysteresis, delayed deformation, and permanent deformation observed in materials, and provided a fundamental basis for subsequent rheological modeling approaches [5].

Osara, J. A., & Bryant, M. D., developed a universal Phenomenological Entropy Generation (PEG) approach that evaluates entropy generation through combined thermodynamic potentials. Their study separates reversible and irreversible energy contributions and provides a comprehensive framework for monitoring entropy generation in engineering processes such as frictional wear, grease degradation, battery charging–discharging, and metal fatigue [6].

Khan, R. et al., investigated the influence of polymers on entropy generation in flow and heat-transfer processes using the FENE-P viscoelastic model. Numerical analyses showed that polymer stress and thermo-diffusion interactions significantly reduce entropy production. The study demonstrates that incorporating polymers can enhance thermodynamic efficiency in engineering systems [7].

Materials and Methods

1. Thermomechanical Properties of Solids

The thermomechanical behavior of solid materials is governed by atomic bonding characteristics, crystal structure, and various types of internal imperfections. This internal structure determines the elastic, viscous, and plastic responses of a material under mechanical loading and temperature variations. During deformation, the applied mechanical energy is partly stored in a recoverable form, while another part is converted into heat through irreversible processes, leading to energy dissipation and entropy generation. In this context, elastic, anelastic, and plastic deformation mechanisms, together with mechanical hysteresis, play a fundamental role in the thermodynamic evaluation of energy storage and energy dissipation processes [8].

Elastic deformation is characterized by a fully recoverable response in which the material returns to its initial state upon removal of the applied stress, representing reversible energy storage. Anelastic deformation, on the other hand, exhibits a delayed recovery after unloading and represents a time-dependent behavior associated with internal damping mechanisms and energy losses. Plastic deformation begins when the applied stress exceeds the yield limit, resulting in permanent, non-recoverable deformation, where a significant portion of the mechanical energy is irreversibly converted into heat. Creep behavior is defined as a time-dependent increase in deformation under constant load, particularly pronounced at elevated temperatures, and reflects the influence of time-dependent internal mechanisms. Mechanical hysteresis arises under cyclic loading–unloading conditions when the stress–strain paths do not coincide; the enclosed hysteresis loop represents the dissipated mechanical energy and is directly related to entropy production [9].

2. Continuum Theory

Continuum theory provides a framework for describing the deformation and thermomechanical behavior of solid materials by treating them as continuous media, without explicitly considering microstructural discontinuities. This approach assumes that field variables such as stress, strain, temperature, and energy are continuous functions of space and time, allowing engineering problems to be formulated mathematically. In this study, the continuum approach is adopted to describe material deformation behavior and to establish a general theoretical framework for the constitutive relations introduced in subsequent sections [10].

Within this framework, thermodynamic concepts are combined with equilibrium and non-equilibrium processes, and material behavior is described based on the conservation of energy and the second law of thermodynamics. Internal energy, heat flux, and entropy are directly linked to the deformation process, and appropriate constitutive relations are derived in accordance with the fundamental axioms of constitutive theory. Continuum theory enables elastic, viscous, and plastic material behaviors to be evaluated within a single, thermodynamically consistent framework, forming the theoretical basis for the rheological models considered in this study [11].

2.1. Mechanical Concepts

a) Strain Rate

The deformation of a solid body is described by the relative displacement of material points under external loads or environmental effects. These displacements represent the extension, contraction, and distortion of the body relative to its reference configuration. Strain is defined through the spatial variation of the displacement field, and under the assumption of small deformations, the true deformation can be separated from rigid-body motions. This assumption ensures that only deformation components contributing to the mechanical response are considered. Deformation can be decomposed into volumetric and distortional contributions, where volumetric deformation represents changes in the total volume, while distortional deformation corresponds to shape changes without volume variation. This distinction provides a fundamental framework for evaluating mechanical behavior in terms of energy storage and energy dissipation mechanisms. Under the assumption of infinitesimal deformations, the strain tensor is defined as [5]:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, u_i denotes the displacement components, x_i represents the position coordinates in the reference configuration, and ε_{ij} denotes the components of the infinitesimal strain tensor.

b) Stress

The mechanical response of a solid body under external loading is described by the concept of stress, which represents the distribution of internal forces within the material. Stress is defined as the force transmitted per unit area across an imaginary internal surface, allowing a local description of the internal state of the body. Under the continuum assumption, the stress state at a point is represented by a second-order stress tensor defined in three-dimensional space. This tensor accounts for both normal and shear effects acting on different material planes and fully characterizes the mechanical state of the material under given loading conditions. Stress quantities are related to external loads through equilibrium equations and play a fundamental role in the evaluation of deformation, yielding, and failure mechanisms. The stress state at a point is defined by the Cauchy stress tensor as [5]:

$$\sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} & \sigma_{12} & \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{21} & \sigma_{22} & \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} & \sigma_{32} & \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here, σ_{ij} represents the stress component acting in the i -direction on a surface normal to the j -direction.

2.2. General Laws

a) Conservation of Mass

The conservation of mass principle states that the total mass of a material body remains constant during deformation. For a material element with initial volume V_0 and density ρ_0 , and deformed volume V and density ρ , the total mass remains unchanged. For an arbitrary material volume moving with the body, the rate of change of mass with respect to time is equal to zero, leading to the fundamental differential form of mass conservation. This relation establishes the continuity condition by linking density variations to the velocity field. The integral form of the mass conservation equation is given as [5]:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_V \rho dV = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here, ρ denotes the local density, V the material (control) volume, and D/Dt the material derivative, indicating that the total mass within the selected volume remains constant with time.

b) Conservation of Momentum

The mechanical behavior of a body in motion within a continuum framework is governed by the conservation of momentum principle. According to this principle, the time rate of change of the total momentum of a material volume is equal to the resultant of external forces acting on that volume. Momentum is defined through the velocity and density fields within the volume, while external forces consist of body forces acting throughout the volume and surface forces transmitted across its boundary. This principle applies to both solids and fluids and forms the basis for establishing the equilibrium relations between the stress field and the motion of the material. The integral form of momentum conservation for a continuum is expressed as [5]:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_V \rho v dV = \int_V \rho f dV + \int_A \sigma n dA \quad (4)$$

Here, ρ is the density, v the velocity vector, V the material volume, f the body force per unit mass, σ the Cauchy stress tensor, and n the outward unit normal vector.

c) Conservation of Energy

The mechanical and thermal behavior of a continuum is described by the principle of energy conservation. According to this principle, the rate of change of the total energy of a material system is equal to the sum of the mechanical work performed on the system and the heat exchanged with its surroundings. Under the continuum assumption, the total energy consists of internal energy and kinetic energy. For quasi-static conditions and small velocities, the variation of kinetic energy may be neglected, and the energy balance is primarily expressed in terms of internal energy. The change in internal energy is associated with the mechanical work of body and surface forces as well as heat transfer across the boundary. The conservation of energy for a continuum can be written as [5]:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_V \rho e dV = \int_V \rho f v dV + \int_A \sigma v n dA - \int_A q n dA \quad (5)$$

Here, ρ is the density, e the internal energy per unit mass, v the velocity vector, f the body force density, σ the stress tensor, q the heat flux vector, V the material volume, and A its boundary surface.

d) Second Law of Thermodynamics

The second law of thermodynamics defines the direction and admissibility of thermodynamic processes. While the first law concerns energy conservation, the second law imposes restrictions on energy transformations, indicating that real processes are accompanied by irreversibilities. These irreversibilities are quantified through the concept of entropy. In the continuum framework, the change in entropy is expressed as the sum of entropy exchange with the surroundings due to heat transfer and entropy production within the system arising from irreversible processes. This formulation provides a thermodynamic basis for analyzing energy dissipation mechanisms associated with mechanical deformation, friction, and viscous effects. For an open continuum system, the entropy balance is written as [5]:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_V \rho s dV = - \int_A \frac{q n}{T} dA + \int_V \rho s^{gen} dV \quad (6)$$

Here, ρ is the density, s the entropy per unit mass, q the heat flux vector, T the absolute temperature, and s^{gen} the entropy production due to irreversible processes.

e) Entropy Production and the Clausius–Duhem Inequality

For continuous media, the second law of thermodynamics implies that irreversible processes occurring during deformation lead to entropy production. Mechanical deformation, friction, viscous effects, and heat conduction represent irreversible mechanisms associated with energy dissipation. Thermodynamic admissibility requires that entropy production remains non-negative at every point within the material. By combining the energy balance with the entropy balance, a constraint condition involving stress, strain rate, and heat conduction terms is obtained. This condition, known as the Clausius–Duhem inequality, serves as a fundamental criterion for evaluating the thermodynamic consistency of constitutive models in continuum mechanics. The local form of the Clausius–Duhem inequality is given by [5]:

$$\dot{s}^{gen} = \frac{1}{T} \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} - \frac{1}{T^2} q_i T_{,i} \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

Here, \dot{s}^{gen} denotes the entropy production rate, q_{ij} the Cauchy stress tensor components, $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$ the strain rate tensor, q_i the heat flux components, T the absolute temperature, and $T_{,i}$ the temperature gradient components.

2.3. Constitutive Theory and Constitutive Relations of Materials

Although the general balance and conservation equations of continuum mechanics are valid for all materials, additional relationships are required to describe the mechanical and thermal characteristics of a specific material in order to close the system of equations. These relationships, referred to as constitutive equations, define the material response to external actions and provide a macroscopic mathematical representation of differences in material behavior [5].

Constitutive equations are commonly expressed in terms of stress, strain, temperature, and their time derivatives. A fundamental requirement for these equations is consistency with experimental observations as well as compliance with the laws of thermodynamics. Constitutive theory establishes the general principles that ensure these relationships are causal, unique, and observer-independent. Within the context of thermomechanical problems, this framework enables elastic, viscous, and plastic behaviors, together with heat transfer and energy dissipation mechanisms, to be modeled in a unified and thermodynamically consistent manner [5].

Findings and Discussion

1. Modeling and Application of General Laws

Rheological models developed to describe the behavior of materials under external loading constitute a powerful approach aimed at representing complex thermomechanical processes by means of simplified mechanical elements. This approach is based on the assumption that the elastic, viscous, and plastic components of material behavior correspond to independent physical processes. Different mechanical elements allow these processes to be mathematically separated, enabling the overall material response to be modeled in a clearer and more interpretable manner [5].

The primary objective of rheological models is to represent time-dependent deformation mechanisms observed in real materials—such as delayed response, permanent deformation, energy dissipation, and hysteresis—using idealized elements with strong physical significance. In this framework, the three principal elements employed are the ideal spring, the ideal dashpot, and the friction element. Each of these elements corresponds to a specific aspect of material behavior [5].

1.1. Ideal Spring (1M1): Elastic Energy-Storing Component

The ideal spring represents an elastic component in which deformation energy is entirely stored and no dissipation mechanism is present. The behavior defined by Hooke's law establishes a linear relationship between stress and strain. Upon removal of the applied load, the element fully recovers its deformation; thus, the process is completely reversible and the associated entropy production is zero. Incorporating the ideal spring into the model enables representation of the instantaneous, energy-storing elastic response of the material. This element forms the mathematical foundation of recoverable deformation in all complex rheological models. Figure 1 shows the 1M1 ideal spring model [5].

Figure 1. 1M1 Ideal Spring Model [5]

The ideal spring is defined by Hooke's law [5]:

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon \quad (8)$$

Stress represents the force acting per unit area, and the elongation of the spring is linearly proportional to the applied force.

The stored elastic energy is expressed accordingly [5]:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} E\varepsilon^2 \quad (9)$$

No dissipation occurs in the system, and the process is entirely reversible.

Figure 2. (a) Equilibrium Deformation of the Ideal Spring, (b) Non-Equilibrium Deformation of the Ideal Spring [5]

Figure 2 shows equilibrium deformation of the ideal spring and non-equilibrium deformation of the ideal spring. Under equilibrium loading, the force increases slowly and the stress–strain curve is represented by a straight line. Under non-equilibrium loading, when the force is applied suddenly, the spring initially exhibits oscillatory motion due to inertial effects (which would not be observed if the spring were assumed massless). Nevertheless, in the long term, the stress–strain relation converges to the same linear behavior. Consequently, the spring model is purely elastic, produces no hysteresis, and does not result in entropy generation [5].

1.2. Ideal Dashpot (1M2): Time-Dependent Viscous Flow

The dashpot element represents purely viscous behavior, where deformation is governed not by the magnitude of strain but by the strain rate. This Newtonian-fluid-like structure is expressed by a flow law in which the applied stress is proportional to the deformation rate. As a result, the dashpot does not store energy; all mechanical work applied to the system is dissipated as heat [5].

This characteristic is of critical importance for representing time-dependent flow phenomena observed in ocean wave motion or molten polymer behavior. The presence of a dashpot in the model causes the system to exhibit irreversible behavior and leads to the emergence of hysteresis during loading–unloading cycles. Figure 3 shows the 1M2 ideal dashpot model [5].

Figure 3. 1M2 Ideal Dashpot Model [5]

A Newtonian fluid analogy is employed [5]:

$$\sigma = \mu \dot{\epsilon} \quad (10)$$

As the applied force increases, the deformation rate increases; however, the deformation itself does not depend directly on the force, but only on its rate.

If the external force increases linearly with time [5]:

$$\sigma = \alpha t \quad (11)$$

Substituting accordingly [5]:

$$\alpha t = \mu \dot{\varepsilon} \rightarrow \dot{\varepsilon} = \frac{\alpha t}{\mu} \quad (12)$$

Taking the integral [5]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\alpha}{2\mu} t^2 \quad (13)$$

This expression is obtained [5]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu\alpha} \quad (14)$$

Under constant force [5]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \rightarrow \varepsilon = \frac{\sigma_0}{\mu} t \quad (15)$$

This indicates that the material behaves as a system flowing at a constant rate.

Figure 4. Deformation of the Ideal Dashpot Element Under (a) Increasing Force and (b) Constant Force [5]

Figure 4 shows deformation of the ideal dashpot element under increasing force and constant force. For increasing force, the stress–strain curve exhibits a concave shape, reflecting the influence of rate dependence. Under constant force, strain increases linearly with time. This schematic illustrates the fluid-like viscous behavior of the 1M2 element [5].

1.3. Friction Element (1M3): Yielding and Permanent Deformation Mechanism

The friction element represents an idealized form of the yielding behavior observed during plastic deformation. This element remains immobile until the applied stress reaches a specified threshold value σ_p ; once the yield stress is attained, sliding occurs at a rate dependent on deformation velocity [5].

Through this mechanism, the model captures permanent deformation of the material. Unlike the elastic element, no energy is stored in the friction element; all mechanical work is converted into heat through friction. Therefore, the friction element constitutes a fully irreversible component of the modeled system. Figure 5 shows the 1M3 friction element model [5].

Figure 5. 1M3 Friction Element Model [5]

The friction force (yield stress) is constant [5]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_p \quad (16)$$

The motion of the model depends on the following condition [5]:

$$|\sigma| < \sigma_p \rightarrow \dot{\varepsilon} = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$|\sigma| = \sigma_p \rightarrow \dot{\varepsilon} > 0 \quad (18)$$

This can be written in the following form [5]:

$$\sigma_p = \frac{1}{\varphi} \dot{\varepsilon} \quad (19)$$

This represents a flow rule indicating that sliding velocity emerges only once the threshold stress is exceeded. No deformation occurs up to $\sigma = \sigma_p$; abrupt deformation begins once $\sigma > \sigma_p$. This behavior results in permanent deformation [5].

1.4. 3M12 Model: Integrated Representation of Elastic, Viscous, and Plastic Behavior

The 3M12 model is a more complex system constructed by combining the three fundamental elements described above according to a specific topology. The spring and dashpot are connected in parallel, and this parallel structure is connected in series with the friction element. This configuration allows the material's instantaneous elastic response, viscous delay, and yielding behavior to be represented simultaneously within a single formulation [5].

The mathematical relations of this model are based on separating the total deformation into elastic and visco-plastic components. By incorporating both time-dependent viscous flow and post-yield permanent deformation, the model captures realistic thermomechanical behavior. The hysteresis observed during loading–unloading cycles demonstrates that the model both stores and dissipates energy [5].

This dissipation is an indication of irreversible processes within the system and is directly associated with energy dissipation and entropy production. Accordingly, the 3M12 model provides a suitable framework for explaining energy transformation mechanisms in materials. Figure 6 shows integrated 3M12 model [5].

Figure 6. Integrated 3M12 Model [5]

In the 3M12 model, the spring and dashpot are connected in parallel, and this parallel structure is connected in series with the friction element. Therefore, the total strain is expressed as [5]:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_{vp} \quad (20)$$

The total stress is given by [5]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_p + \sigma_{vp} \quad (21)$$

The relationship between the dashpot and the spring is written as [5]:

$$\mu(\dot{\varepsilon} - \dot{\varepsilon}_e) = \sigma - \sigma_p \quad (22)$$

From the Hookean element [5]:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_e = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} \quad (23)$$

Substituting yields [5]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_p + \mu \left(\dot{\varepsilon} - \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} \right) \quad (24)$$

Loading condition ($\sigma = at + \sigma_p$) [5].

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_p}{E} + \frac{(\sigma - \sigma_p)^2}{2\mu\alpha} \quad (25)$$

Unloading condition ($\sigma = -at + 2\sigma_0$) [5].

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_p}{E} + \frac{1}{2\mu\alpha} \left[2(\sigma_0 - \sigma_p)^2 - (\sigma - \sigma_p)^2 \right] \quad (26)$$

Finally, for $\sigma > \sigma_p$ [5].

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{\mu} (\sigma - \sigma_p)t + \frac{\sigma - \sigma_p}{E} \quad (27)$$

The loading and unloading curves do not coincide, resulting in hysteresis. The area enclosed between these curves represents energy loss. This energy is converted into heat, leading to positive entropy production. Consequently, the 3M12 model accurately represents complex elastic, visco-plastic, irreversible, and energy-dissipative material behavior [5].

2. Numerical Analysis of Energy Dissipation and Entropy Generation

In this study, an example case study is constructed based on a three-element rheological model that simultaneously represents elastic, viscous, and plastic behaviors. The model is defined with a topology similar to the 3M12 rheological structure, in which the spring and dashpot elements are connected in series, while the friction element is connected in parallel to this structure. Numeric analysis was performed using the MSC Marc-Mentat program. The geometric configuration of the model is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The Geometric Model

In the numerical analyses performed on the constructed model, the initial temperature of the system is assumed to be 300 K, and the structure is subjected to a constant velocity of 4.5 m/s. The stiffness coefficient of the spring is defined as $k = 2000 \text{ N/m}$, while the damping coefficient of the dashpot element is specified as $c = 200 \text{ N}\cdot\text{s/m}$. The analyzed structure is considered as a steel system with a total mass of 8 kg. The numerical analysis configuration of the system is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. The Numerical Model

In Figure 9, the displacement–time relationship obtained from the numerical analyses is presented. The displacement response reflects the overall system behavior resulting from the combined action of the elements defined in the rheological model.

Figure 9. Displacement–time curve

In Figure 10, the time-dependent variation of the damping energy generated in the dashpot element is shown. The increase in damping energy directly represents the mechanical energy dissipation occurring in the system. The obtained results are consistent with the viscous flow and irreversible energy dissipation mechanisms discussed in the theoretical section.

Figure 10. Time-dependent variation of damping energy

In Figure 11, the time-dependent variation of the total mechanical work performed on the system by external loads is presented. The total work includes both the elastically stored energy and the energy dissipated through damping and friction mechanisms. This graph provides an overall view of the energy transformation processes in the system and exhibits behavior consistent with the theoretical energy balance.

Figure 11. Time-dependent variation of total work

In Figure 12, the time-dependent variation of entropy generation, calculated using the energy dissipation components obtained from the numerical analyses, is shown. The continuous increase in entropy generation is a consequence of the irreversible processes occurring within the system. This behavior is consistent with the energy–entropy relationships presented in the theoretical section and the Clausius–Duhem inequality, demonstrating the thermodynamic validity of the proposed model.

Figure 12. Time-dependent variation of entropy generation

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, a three-element rheological model with a topology similar to the 3M12 structure was numerically investigated to examine the coupled elastic, viscous, and plastic behavior of solid materials within a thermodynamically consistent framework. By combining continuum thermodynamics with rheological modeling, the relationship between mechanical energy dissipation and entropy generation was explicitly evaluated.

The numerical results demonstrate that the proposed model successfully captures key features of irreversible deformation processes, including time-dependent displacement, energy dissipation through damping and friction mechanisms, and the associated entropy production. The displacement response reflects the combined action of elastic, viscous, and plastic components, while the damping energy and total mechanical work clearly indicate irreversible energy losses. The monotonic increase in entropy generation confirms that dissipation processes are consistently accompanied by positive entropy production, in agreement with the Clausius–Duhem inequality and the second law of thermodynamics.

The findings show that energy-based quantities obtained from numerical analyses, such as dissipated mechanical energy, can be effectively used to evaluate entropy generation in rheological models. This provides a physically transparent interpretation of irreversible processes and offers a practical approach for assessing thermodynamic consistency in numerical simulations of deforming solids. The results also highlight the capability of the 3M12-type rheological model to represent hysteresis behavior and irreversible energy transformations in a unified formulation.

Based on these outcomes, future studies may focus on extending the present model to more complex loading conditions, such as cyclic or non-proportional loading paths, in order to further investigate hysteresis and accumulation of plastic deformation. Additionally, incorporating temperature-dependent material parameters and fully coupled thermo-mechanical analyses would allow more accurate evaluation of heat generation and entropy production. Finally, applying the proposed approach to experimental data or more detailed finite element models would provide further validation and enhance its applicability to real engineering materials and structures.

References

- [1] Reyes, S., Lopez, E. L., Vassiliou, M. F., & Konstantinidis, D. (2024). Modeling of a thermoplastic-polyurethane and its potential for energy dissipation devices. *In 18th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering (WCEE 2024)*.
- [2] Chokoe, I., Makinde, O. D., & Monaledi, R. L. (2024). Analysis of entropy generation in unsteady flow of nanofluids past a convectively heated moving permeable cylindrical surface. *Archives of Thermodynamics*, 45(3).
- [3] Gurt, A., & Khonsari, M. (2024). A review of the rheological consistency of materials. *Lubricants*, 12(7), 236.
- [4] Aggarwal, A., Hackel, N., Grunert, F., Ilisch, S., Beiner, M., & Blume, A. (2024). Investigation of Rheological, Mechanical, and Viscoelastic Properties of Silica-Filled SSBR and BR Model Compounds. *Polymers*, 16(22), 3212.
- [5] Özdemir, M. (1990). Malzemelerin şekil değiştirme modelleri ve entropi üretimi. *Yüksek Lisans Tezi, İTÜ*.
- [6] Osara, J. A., & Bryant, M. D. (2024). Methods to calculate entropy generation. *Entropy*, 26(3), 237.
- [7] Khan, R., Rossi di Schio, E., & Valdiserri, P. (2024). Entropy optimization of a FENE-P viscoelastic model: a numerically guided comprehensive analysis. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 149(23), 13953-13965.
- [8] Diab, A., You, L., Topa, A., Saboo, N., Sukhija, M., & Awed, A. (2024). Modeling linear and nonlinear viscoelastic oscillatory rheometric stress-strain hysteresis of asphalt binders. *Scientific reports*, 14(1), 28499.
- [9] Panoskaltzis, V. P. (2025). Energy Dissipation in Engineering Materials and Structures by Using the Laws of Thermodynamics. *Thermo*, 5(2), 20.
- [10] Sawangikar, M. S., Chopra, P. K. P., Burande, B. C., & Waghe, P. (2025). Comprehensive review of Rational Irreversible Thermodynamics. *Chemical Review and Letters*, 8(1), 137-143.
- [11] Zbiciak, A., Kraśkiewicz, C., Wasilewski, K., Mossakowski, P., & Płudowska-Zagrajek, M. (2025). Mechanical Modelling of Static Hysteresis in Under Ballast Mats Using a Novel Rheological Approach. *Materials*, 18(23), 5301.